

Diels-Alder reaction with the $>C=P-$ functionality of annelated 1,3-azaphospholes[†]

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Abstract : The Diels-Alder reactions of the $>C=P-$ functionality in annelated 1,3-azaphospholes and their diaza-analogues have been reviewed. The article includes experimental and theoretical results accomplished in the author's (RKB) laboratories.

Keywords : Diels-Alder reaction, annelated 1,3-azaphospholes, annelated 1,4,2-diazaphospholes, stereoselectivity, regioselectivity, DFT calculations.

Introduction and scope of the review

In the year 1988, we developed a simple method for the synthesis of 1,3-azaphospholo[1,5-*a*]pyridine derivative (**1**) from the reaction of 2-ethyl-1-phenacylpyridinium bromide with PCl_3 and Et_3N and the basic skeleton was named as 2-phosphaindolizine¹ perceiving it to result from replacing CH moiety at the 2-position of the indolizine skeleton² (**2**) by a two-coordinate, trivalent (σ^2, λ^3) phosphorous atom. This method turned out to be of general applicability as it could be extended not only to the syntheses of 2-phospha analogues of 1-aza-, 3-aza- and 1,3-diazaindolizines but also to the preparation of 1,3-azaphospholes annelated to other heterocyclic systems, such as thiazole, benzothiazole and oxazole.

Subsequently, we succeeded in developing another simple method involving the reaction of alkoxy-carbonyl-

methylpyridinium bromides with PCl_3 and Et_3N that made 1,3-bis(alkoxycarbonyl)-1,3-azaphospholo[1,5-*a*]pyridines (**3**) available³. Although an isoquinoline analogue of **3** could be prepared in similar manner⁴, this method, however, could not be extended to other heterocyclic systems, such as thiazole and benzothiazole. As we shall see later, the compound **3** shows special reactivity, which is missing in the compound **1**.

By following these two methods, our hands were soon full of a rich crop of annelated 1,3-azaphospholes. Then we focused our attention on investigating their reactivities and to our pleasant surprise, these compounds proved to be quite fertile and could be used as templates for obtaining a variety of organophosphorus compounds. In the meantime, we developed computational facilities in our research group with the active support of our Ger-

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

man collaborators. With the help of computational calculations, we could investigate successfully the reaction mechanisms and rationalize the observed stereo- and regioselectivities in the Diels-Alder (DA) reactions with the $>C=P-$ functionality of the synthesized 1,3-azaphospholes. Thus within a decade, rich and interesting chemistry in a frontier area of organophosphorus chemistry developed in our research group.

In this mini-review, we intend to restrict ourselves to overviewing the chemistry of the DA reactions with the $>C=P-$ functionality of the annelated 1,3-azaphospholes synthesized in our laboratories. The methods of preparation of these starting compounds and details of their other reactions will not be included and can be found in our other recent reviews⁵⁻⁷. Furthermore, this article includes mainly the work on the DA reactions with the $>C=P-$ functionality carried out in our laboratories covering the literature right from the beginning till the latest results. Our comprehensive review "The Diels-Alder reactions involving $>C=P-$ functionality" includes our results published till the year 2008 besides other work in this field⁸.

We hope that this mini-review will help not only in sustaining the interest in this field of organophosphorus compounds having phosphorus atom in the low co-ordination state, but will also succeed in identifying potential research directions.

Electronic structure of the $>C=P-$ functionality and energetics of its DA reaction

The carbon-phosphorus π -bond in the $>C=P-$ functionality is expected to be weaker than the carbon-carbon π -bond due to weaker $2p-3p$ overlapping in the former. In fact, the $>C=P-$ π -bond is only 60–70% as strong as the $>C=C<$ π -bond⁹. As a consequence of this, the activation energy barrier for the DA reaction with the $>C=P-$ functionality is expected to be lower than that for the DA reaction with the $>C=C<$ functionality. Theoretical calculations confirm it (Fig. 1)¹⁰.

It may be noted that the $\text{HOMO}_{\text{diene}}\text{-LUMO}_{\text{phosphaethene}}$ gap (4.55 eV) is much smaller than that between $\text{HOMO}_{\text{diene}}\text{-LUMO}_{\text{ethene}}$ (6.32 eV). Accordingly, on the basis of FMO theory, the DA reaction of phosphaethene is expected to be much faster with a lower activation barrier than that of ethene. A more or less similar pattern prevails when the $>C=P-$ functionality is integrated in the aromatic sextet, except that the activation barrier for the DA reaction is raised and more vigorous conditions (higher temperature, use of catalyst) become necessary.

DA reactions of annelated 1,3-azaphospholes

DA reactions of 1,3-azaphospholo[1,5-a]pyridines :

In contrast to indolizines, which do not undergo DA reaction, we have successfully carried out DA reactions with the $>C=P-$ functionality of 1,3-bis(alkoxycarbonyl)-[1,3]azaphospholo[1,5-a]pyridines i.e. 1,3-bis(alkoxy-

Fig. 1. Frontier molecular orbitals of phosphaethene, 1,3-butadiene and ethene at B3LYP/6-31+G(d,p)¹⁰.

carbonyl)-2-phosphaindolizines with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene and with isoprene (Scheme 1)^{4,11}.

The reaction is carried out in the presence of sulfur or

3-Ethoxycarbonyl-1-methyl-2-phosphaindolizine (**1**, R¹=Me, R²=CO₂Et) did not undergo DA reaction with DMB alone or in the presence of sulfur even on refluxing

Scheme 1

methyl iodide, in the absence of which the reaction is slow and does not proceed to completion. The role of sulfur or methyl iodide is to push a reversible DA reaction in the forward direction by oxidizing the σ^3, λ^3 -phosphorus atom of the initially formed cycloadduct. The reactions occur with complete stereo-/regio-selectivities, except the reaction of 1,2-bis(ethoxycarbonyl)-[1,3]-azaphospholo[5,1-*a*]isoquinolone (**3**, R¹R² = -CH=CH-CH=CH-, R³=H) with isoprene in the presence of methyl iodide when two regioisomers are formed, the major one being 62% (**7**, R¹R² = -CH=CH-CH=CH-, R³=H, R⁴=H). The structure of **5** (R¹R² = -CH=CH-CH=CH-, R³=H, R⁴=H) was confirmed by single crystal X-ray diffraction studies¹¹. The DA reactions of **3** (R¹R² = -CH=CH-CH=CH-, R³=H) could be accomplished much faster under microwave irradiation without affecting the yields and the stereo- and regio-selectivities¹².

The observed stereo- and regio-selectivities in the DA reactions of 2-phosphaindolizines have been rationalized on the basis of the theoretical calculations at the DFT level¹³.

in toluene¹². To look into the unexpected inertness of 2-phosphaindolizine substituted by EWG at 3-position, we computed the following four model DA reactions at the DFT (B3LYP/6-31G**) level (Scheme 2)¹⁴.

Scheme 2

Computed model DA reactions of 2-phosphaindolizines with 1,3-butadiene.

Reaction No.	R ¹	R ²	ΔE_a (kcal mol ⁻¹)	ΔE_{rxn} (kcal mol ⁻¹)
1	H	H	27.52	+0.76
2	H	CO ₂ Me	29.49	+8.17
3	CO ₂ Me	H	24.55	-5.05
4	CO ₂ Me	CO ₂ Me	22.43	-0.92

It is noteworthy that the activation energy barrier for the DA reaction of 3-methoxycarbonyl-2-phosphaindolizine (Reaction no. 2) is the highest (29.49 kcal mol⁻¹); it is higher than that even for the DA reaction of the unsubstituted 2-phosphaindolizine (Reaction no. 1), having no EWG at the 3-position. The NBO analysis reveals the existence of an interesting phenomenon. The bridge-head nitrogen acting as an electron pool donates its lone-pair to the five-membered azaphosphole ring. The presence of an EWG at the 3-position accentuates this effect further and makes the >C=P- functionality an electron-rich dienophile that does not undergo DA reaction with an electron-rich diene like DMB. However in the case of **3** (R¹=R²= CO₂Me), the EWG at 1-position acts as a sink between the nitrogen lone-pair and the >C=P- functionality (Fig. 2) retaining the latter still sufficiently electron deficient so that it undergoes DA reaction with DMB as observed with 1,3-bis(alkoxycarbonyl)-2-phosphaindolizines described earlier.

Fig. 2. Electron donation by bridge-head nitrogen atom in 2-phosphaindolizines.

Then we investigated the effect of organo-aluminium chloride catalysts on the dienophilic reactivity of indolizine and 2-phosphaindolizines towards DA reaction with 1,3-butadiene theoretically at the DFT level (B3LYP/6-31+G**) ¹⁵. Co-ordination of the organoaluminium catalyst with the oxygen atom of the carbonyl group of indolizine or 2-phosphaindolizine, instead of lowering the activation energy barrier, raises it, for its DA reaction with 1,3-butadiene as compared to the activation energy

barrier for the DA reaction of the uncomplexed indolizine or 2-phosphaindolizine with 1,3-butadiene (Scheme 3) ¹⁵.

It is obvious that co-ordination of a Lewis acid with the oxygen atom of the carbonyl group makes the bridge-head nitrogen atom donate its lone-pair still more efficiently making the dienophilic moiety, >C=Z- (Z=CH or P) more electron-rich as compared to that in the uncomplexed indolizine or 2-phosphaindolizine. It explains why no DA reaction of indolizine having EWG at the 3-position has been accomplished even in the presence of a Lewis acid as catalyst. 2-Phosphaindolizine, however, has another site, i.e. σ^2, λ^3 -phosphorus atom to co-ordinate with the Lewis acid. On computing the DA reaction of 2-phosphaindolizine complexed to AlCl₃ at the σ^2, λ^3 -P atom with 1,3-butadiene, there is remarkable lowering of the activation energy barrier; it comes down to 22.57 kcal mol⁻¹ only (Scheme 4) ¹⁵.

Encouraged by these results, we successfully carried out the DA reactions of 2-phosphaindolizines having EWG at 3-position only (**1**) with DMB in the presence of ethylaluminium dichloride as catalyst (Scheme 5) ¹⁶.

In continuation to it, we carried out the DA reaction of 2-phosphaindolizine- η^1 -P-aluminium(O-menthoxy) dichloride complex **11** with DMB, when [2+4] cycloadducts are formed with complete diastereoselectivity (Scheme 6) ¹⁷. Computational calculations at the DFT level

Maheshwari *et al.* : Diels-Alder reaction with the >C=P- functionality of annelated *etc.*

Scheme 3. Computed model DA reactions of indolizines (Z=CH) and 2-phosphaindolizines (Z=P) with 1,3-butadiene at B3LYP/6-31+G**.

Scheme 4. Computed model DA reaction of (σ^2 , λ^3 -P-AlCl₃)-2-phosphaindolizine with 1,3-butadiene at B3LYP/6-31+G**.

Scheme 5. Diels-Alder reaction of 2-phosphaindolizines with DMB catalyzed by ethylaluminum dichloride.

(B3LYP/6-31+G*) reveals that the O-methoxy moiety blocks the *Re* face of the >C=P- functionality due to which diene attacks on the *Si* face only¹⁷.

DA reactions of 1,3-azaphospholo[5,1-b]benzothiazole :

1,3-Azaphospholo[5,1-*b*]benzothiazole (**13**) undergoes DA reaction with 1,3-dienes only in the presence of oxy-

gen, sulfur, or selenium, the reaction with isoprene occurring with complete regioselectivity (Scheme 7)¹⁸.

*DA reactions of 1,4,2-diazaphospholo[4,5-*a*]pyridines :*

1,4,2-Diazaphospholo[4,5-*a*]pyridines, i.e. 1-aza-2-phosphaindolizines also undergo DA reactions in the presence of sulfur or selenium. The reactions proceed with

Scheme 6. Diels-Alder reaction of 2-phosphaindolizine- η^1 -P-aluminium(O-menthoxy) dichloride with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene.

Scheme 7

complete stereoselectivity. As regards the regioselectivity, the reaction of 7-methyl-1-aza-2-phosphaindolizine (**15**) with isoprene and selenium afforded two regioisomers in the ratio of 4 : 1. Furthermore, that the role of sulfur or methyl iodide is to oxidize the phosphorus atom of the initially formed cycloadduct is confirmed by the fact that in one case, reaction could be completed in the absence of the oxidizing agent too, but only after refluxing in chloroform for 24 days¹⁹. Besides, the reaction of **15** with 2,3-dimethylbutadiene and methyl iodide gave the N-alkylated product **16** (R=Me) which confirms unam-

biguously that [2+4] cycloaddition precedes the oxidation of the phosphorus atom. The reaction with isoprene under these conditions afforded two regioisomers **16** (R=H) and **16'** in the ratio of 7 : 3 (Scheme 8)¹⁹.

The observed stereo- and regio-selectivities have been rationalized on the basis of the theoretical calculations at the DFT level¹⁹.

DA reactions of thiazolo[3,2-d][1,4,2]diazaphospholes and their 5,6-dihydro and benzo derivatives :

We have also accomplished successfully DA reactions

Maheshwari *et al.* : Diels-Alder reaction with the $>C=P-$ functionality of annelated *etc.*

Scheme 8. DA reaction of 1-aza-2-phosphaindolizine in the presence of methyl iodide.

Scheme 9

of thiazolo[3,2-*d*][1,4,2]diazaphospholes and their 5,6-dihydro- and benzo- derivatives (Scheme 9). These reactions also occur with high stereo- and regio-selectivities. 3-Unsubstituted [1,4,2]diazaphospholo[5,4-*b*]benzothiazole (23, R¹ = H), however, on reaction with isoprene yielded two regioisomers, 24 (R = R¹ = H) and 24' in 2 : 1 ratio¹⁸.

The observed stereo- and regio-selectivities in the above reactions have been rationalized on the basis of the DFT calculations^{20,21}. The reactions occur via pericyclic mechanism, aromatic character of the transition structures, which are asynchronous, being confirmed by high negative NICS values. The observed *endo* stereoselectivity and *para* : *meta* regioselectivity could be rationalized on the basis of secondary molecular orbital (SMO) interactions in the respective transition states. The calculated ratios of the *endo/exo* stereoisomers as well as those of the *meta/para* regioisomers agree nicely with the experimental results.

Conclusions

The >C=P- functionality in the annelated azaphospholes is more reactive than the >C=C< functionality in the non-phosphorus analogues as dienophiles in the DA reactions with dimethylbutadiene and isoprene. If necessary, the DA reactions can be catalyzed by the Lewis acid, such as ethylaluminium dichloride. The reactions occur stereo- and regio-selectively. On using a chiral catalyst, such as (O-menthoxy)aluminium dichloride, the DA reaction of 3-(ethoxycarbonyl)-1-methyl-2-phosphaindolizine with DMB occurs with complete diastereoselectivity.

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